

COPING STRATEGIES IN WOMEN WITH DIFFERENT EXPERIENCES OF VIOLENCE: A STUDY FROM UZBEKISTAN

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Background and Theoretical Foundations. Violence represents a prolonged destructive factor that causes profound disruption of the personality's adaptive mechanisms. The specific character of coping with the consequences of traumatic experience is determined by the nature and intensity of external pressure. Chronic frustration of basic needs for safety and autonomy narrows the range of available coping strategies, shifting the focus from active transformation of the environment toward intrapsychic self-defense and passive adjustment to crisis conditions. The aim of this study was to examine the specific features of coping behavior in women depending on their current status of violence exposure.

Empirical Basis of the Study. The Ways of Coping Questionnaire (R. Lazarus, S. Folkman) was used as the primary diagnostic instrument. Statistical analysis of the raw data was conducted using nonparametric methods (Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis H test, Spearman rank correlation coefficient).

The total sample consisted of 225 female respondents recruited from three regions of Uzbekistan: Bukhara region, Tashkent region, and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Based on case history data and current relationship status, participants were divided into two main groups: those currently experiencing violence (N = 117; 52% of the sample) and those living outside a situation of violence (N = 108; 48%). For more in-depth analysis, the second group was further subdivided: 63 women (28%) in intact normative relationships without manifestations of aggression, and 45 women (20%) who had fully terminated a destructive relationship with a former partner.

Results and Discussion. Comparative analysis using the Mann-Whitney U test revealed a qualitative dichotomy in the structure of coping behavior depending on the presence or absence of traumatic experience. The empirical values and significance levels of these differences are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Statistical Significance of Differences in Coping Strategies among Women (Mann-Whitney U Test)

Indicators	Mean Rank		Mann-Whitney U	Significance Level (p)
	Currently experiencing violence	Not currently		

	N=117	experiencing violence N=108		
Confrontive Coping	95,58	131,87	4280,000	0.000*
Distancing	135,29	88,85	3709,500	0.000*
Self-Controlling	123,54	101,58	5085,000	0.011*
Seeking Social Support	97,32	129,98	4484,000	0.000*
Accepting Responsibility	137,04	86,95	3505,000	0.000*
Escape-Avoidance	136,06	88,01	3619,500	0.000*
Planful Problem Solving	93,11	134,55	3990,500	0.000*
Positive Reappraisal	106,15	120,42	5516,500	0.099

Note: * – differences are significant at $p < 0.05$; ** – differences are significant at $p < 0.01$.

Among respondents currently experiencing violence ($N=117$), a statistically significantly higher preference was found for the following intrapsychic strategies: “Distancing” ($p=0.000$), “Self-Controlling” ($p=0.011$), “Accepting Responsibility” ($p=0.000$) and “Escape-Avoidance” ($p=0.000$). These defensive mechanisms are directed inward and serve to reduce the intensity of distress under conditions of inability to control the external environment.

In contrast, women outside the situation of violence ($N=108$) significantly more frequently rely on problem-focused and socially oriented coping: “Confrontive Coping”, “Planful Problem Solving”, and “Seeking Social Support” ($p=0.000$), indicating the restoration of their behavioral agency. The absence of significant differences on the “Positive Reappraisal” scale ($p=0.099$) points to a tendency toward invariance of this mechanism: although the differences do not reach statistical significance ($p=0.099$), the obtained value suggests its stable compensatory function across all stages of working through psychological trauma.

To examine the dynamics of transformation in coping behavior during the process of gradually leaving a destructive environment, the sample was further differentiated into three groups using the Kruskal-Wallis H test, which allowed the patterns of coping transformation to be identified in the course of progressive disengagement from the destructive environment (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparative Analysis of Coping Behavior in Women by Current Relationship Status (Kruskal-Wallis H Test)

Indicators	Mean Rank			Kruskal-Wallis H	Significance Level (p)
	Group 1:	Group 2: violence absent,	Group 3: relations hip		

	violence present N=117	relationship intact (N = 63)	terminated (N = 45)		
Confrontive Coping	95,58	136,60	125,24	18,323	0.000*
Distancing	135,29	98,04	75,98	31,744	0.001*
Self-Controlling	123,54	104,62	97,33	6,792	0.034
Seeking Social Support	97,32	123,52	139,03	15,688	0.001*
Accepting Responsibility	137,04	92,11	79,73	34,612	0.001*
Escape-Avoidance	136,06	96,42	76,24	33,272	0.001*
Planful Problem Solving	93,11	134,57	134,52	22,856	0.001*
Positive Reappraisal	106,15	129,8	107,26	5,918	0.052

Note: * – differences are significant at $p < 0.05$.

In the situation of prolonged contact with an abuser (Group 1), defensive-passive patterns (“Distancing”, “Escape”) predominate, functioning as a psychological barrier. When the family context normalizes without manifestations of aggression (Group 2), increases in “Confrontive Coping” and “Planful Problem Solving” are recorded, which serve as markers of the restoration of agency and readiness to openly confront difficulties. Complete termination of the destructive relationship (Group 3) is accompanied by the highest expression of the “Seeking Social Support” strategy (mean rank 139.03; $p=0.001$), reflecting a reorientation of attention from autistic self-protection toward active engagement with the social environment.

Intercorrelation analysis (Spearman) confirmed the suppressive effect of destructive experience on constructive coping potential (Table 3).

Table 3. Correlation Matrix between Violence Modalities and Coping Strategies (Spearman’s r)

	Violence Index	Control and Restriction of Freedom	Emotional and Psychological Violence	Economic Violence	Sexual Violence	Physical Violence

Confrontive Coping	-0.237**	-0.075	-0.249**	-0.161*	-0.317**	-0.214**
Distancing	0.219**	0.104	0.261**	0.123	0.198**	0.135*
Self-Controlling	0.155*	0.163*	0.186**	0.068	0.103	0.121
Seeking Social Support	0.187**	-0.025	-0.195**	-0.190**	-0.276**	-0.124
Accepting Responsibility	0.076	0.025	0.148*	0.037	0.087	0.016
Escape-Avoidance	0.119	-0.019	0.297**	0.076	0.054	0.056
Planful Problem Solving	-0.137*	0.041	-0.186**	-0.151*	-0.192**	-0.142*
Positive Reappraisal	-0.125	0.015	-0.156*	-0.034	-0.199**	-0.187**

Note: * – correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$; ** – correlation is significant at $p < 0.01$.

According to the obtained matrix, the overall violence index shows significant negative correlations with the “Confrontive Coping” ($r=-0.237$; $p<0.01$), “Planful Problem Solving” ($r=-0.137$; $p<0.05$), and “Seeking Social Support” ($r=-0.187$; $p<0.01$) strategies. Simultaneously, positive associations are recorded with “Distancing” ($r=0.219$; $p<0.01$) and “Self-Controlling” ($r=0.155$; $p<0.05$).

Differentiated analysis of pairwise associations revealed the following patterns:

1. **Emotional and Psychological Violence** inflicts the most pervasive damage on the coping system, provoking a reduction of proactive coping and initiating maladaptive patterns of “Escape-Avoidance” ($r=0.297$; $p<0.01$) and “Accepting Responsibility” ($r=0.148$; $p<0.05$) — the latter being interpreted as a self-blame mechanism characteristic of victims of chronic violence (Walker, 1979).

2. **Economic pressure** acts as a predictor of reduced activity in overcoming difficulties, showing negative associations with confrontation, problem-solving, and help-seeking.

3. **Physical and sexual aggression** rigidly block the capacity for open resistance and planning, driving respondents into passive withdrawal from an unbearable reality (marked negative associations with problem-solving and positive reappraisal, positive associations with distancing).

4. **Conclusions.** Thus, a profound disruption of the entire coping structure under the influence of violent experience has been empirically demonstrated in a representative sample of 225 women. Increasing intensity of aggression narrows the repertoire of proactive, adaptive techniques, compelling the individual to rely on passive intrapsychic defense. The dynamics of disengagement from the source of threat are characterized by a sequential transition from reactive, avoidance-based strategies toward proactive, socially open, and goal-directed crisis management. The findings may be applied in the development of differentiated psychological support programs for women who have experienced violence, taking into account their stage of exit from destructive relationships.

